

Moving Towards Total Cabin Filtration: Realtime Monitoring

Chris Savage, Stephen Simpson, Paul Roux

Pall Corporation, New Port Richey, USA

Corresponding author:

Chris Savage

christopher_savage@europe.pall.com

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air quality sensors, fume events, cabin air, contaminants, volatile organic compounds

ABBREVIATIONS

VOC Volatile organic compounds

ABSTRACT

It is difficult for airline crews to identify odors that cause expensive delays and unscheduled maintenance. The Pall Cabin Air Quality Sensor (CAQS) identifies the source of an odor by utilizing aerospace qualified microelectronics technology, enabling focused maintenance, increasing up-time and reducing cost.

INTRODUCTION

Pall has been serving the aerospace industry for over 70 years with innovative, enabling products. Pall was the first company to develop and introduce hospital-grade (H14) HEPA filters in the aircraft cabin air recirculation line and Pall Aerospace now proudly leads the way in the development and introduction of sensors that will identify contaminants present in the cabin that have been introduced in the fresh air supply.

Statistics show that about a third of delays are due to events not associated with weather or air traffic control (ATC). These delays include fume events, where noxious odors are detected in the cockpit or passenger cabin and whilst it is recognized that fume events happen infrequently, it can be difficult to identify the source which can lead to significant maintenance activities and the aircraft being out of operation.

The frequency of reported air quality incidents has increased over the years and this increase is due not to age-related deteriorating aircraft performance but more to an increased awareness of cabin air quality among flight crew and passengers and also improved crew training related to reporting procedures for fume events.¹

While volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are generated from many sources, including sources inside the cabin, the VOCs from engine fluids, primarily lube oils, create the most concerns in the industry. These VOCs can stem from oil leaking past seals into the hot engine bleed air. The vaporization, partial oxidation, or combustion of that oil creates VOCs, some of which are or can become toxic.^{2,3} Since engine bleed air is used for the fresh air supply, these VOCs can then enter the cabin and cockpit. Fume events are disruptive because identifying an errant smell is time consuming and crew members are not always able to detect the source. According to a report by the German BFU, 65% of all odors reported in the cabin are unknown or not determined, therefore a sensor that can confirm if the odor emanated from the fresh air supply or not would be a very valuable tool in facilitating the maintenance activities and returning the aircraft to service in a shorter space of time.

Cabin air quality sensor

Boston Micro Systems, a division of Pall Aerospace have developed a MEMS (Micro Electro Mechanical Systems) based sensor that is capable of identifying selected VOCs that are present in the aircraft cabin. Pall have demonstrated the sensor's capability in the laboratory and are now manufacturing advanced prototypes which will be available for flight trials.

The sensor is designed to meet the following aims:

- Improves efficiency of maintenance activities by enabling rapid location of failures
- Enables predictive maintenance (identifying trend of VOC levels in line with impending failures)
- Enables pilot decision to fly post fume event (without the need for aircraft maintenance or engineers to inspect prior to flight)
- Ensures a pro-active approach by improving overall cabin air quality for crew and passengers

Figure 1 — The sensor module

The technologies on which the sensors are built are well proven and are used in such well known and established products such as mobile telephones. Pall's MEMS division originally took this core technology and adapted it to enable the detection of moisture in the semiconductor fabrication process gasses to concentrations as low as parts per trillion (PPT), this is necessary to ensure a high manufacture yield. The technology was further developed to enable the detection of explosive compounds which then evolved to detection of cabin air contaminants.

Operating principle

The sensor is an electronic nose; this means that it enables identification of complex mixes of compounds (such as those that form "burnt oil") rather than specific molecules (e.g. toluene). The sensor module, which is no more than 2.3 mm square (Figure 1), is comprised of eight individual sensors. Each sensor has two layers: 1) a pre concentrator which collects the contaminants from the air stream and 2) the resonating layer which generates the responses from which the contaminants can be deduced (Figure 2). The contaminants are released from the pre concentrator with a periodic flash of heat. The released contaminants then interact with the chemo-selective coating on the sensor downstream and the contaminant "smell" is identified by factors such as the change in the sensor resonance (Figure 3).

Figure 2 — The resonating layer

Figure 3 — Identification of contaminants

These properties are then used to generate pattern recognition algorithms which enable accurate identification of the fluid in multi-dimensional feature space. Figure 4 shows the increase in resolution that occurs when just moving from 2D to 3D feature space. Specifically, two sensors alone are not enough to

Feature: Maximum Response During First 0.2sec of Preconcentrator Flash

Figure 4 — Increase in resolution moving from 2D to 3D

Alpha-3 Prototype 2D Feature Projection

Figure 5 — Identification of contaminants

discriminate water and Windex while the distinction is immediately clear when just one more sensor is added to the detection array.

This same approach has been used in detecting the target fluids in the cabin air during ground-based testing on an A320 and Figure 5 demonstrates that the sensor uniquely identifies the contaminants even in 2D and the differentiation will be further enhanced when the pattern recognition algorithms are finalized.

Pall are still in the process of defining the fingerprint of the normal cabin air environment to establish a generic profile (pattern) so that any deviations from this can be reliably identified so the sensor will not register a fume or smell event when it is actually a change in the background and part of a normal flight profile. Mark 1 production sensors will be manufactured in Q1, 2019 and these will further characterize the cabin air.

References

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